

Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 62 (0000 up to ####)

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Historic Overview

Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Inder Taneja published five papers on arXiv (for 1 up to 11111):

ARXIV Version	Evaluated Range	Allowed Operations	Missing Increasing	Missing Decreasing	Valid Representations
1 (06-02-2013) ¹	44 to 1000	+ * ^	2	10	1902 (of 1914)
2 (19-03-2013) ²	44 to 4444	+ * ^	50	53	8699 (of 8802)
3 (05-06-2013) ³	44 to 11111	+ * ^ ()	590	605	20941 (of 22136)
4 (05-08-2013) ⁴	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () -	449	315	21460 (of 22224)
5 (08-01-2014) ⁵	0 to 11111	+ * ^ () - /	9	10	22205 (of 22224)

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (for -2147483647 up to 2147483647):

Date	Title
12-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Exhaustive Search ⁶
14-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Negative Integers ⁷
18-06-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Without Subtraction and/or Division ⁸

Inder Taneja published three papers on RGMIA (for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
12-09-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000 ⁹
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000 ¹⁰
10-11-2018	Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000 ¹¹

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (comparing results for 11112 up to 30000):

Date	Title
06-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: 11112 up to 30000 ¹²

Authors published three papers on Figshare/Zenodo (improving our previous work):

Date	Title
14-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Simplifications (01) ¹³
24-12-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (01) ¹⁴
02-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (02) ¹⁵
28-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Fill the Gaps (03) ²⁶

Historic Overview

Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Tim Wylie published one paper on arXiv (focusing on bases 3 through 10):

Date	Title
11-10-2018	Crazy Sequential Representations of Numbers for Small Bases ¹⁶

Authors published six papers on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 11 through 16):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 (0000 up to AAAA) ¹⁷
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 12 (0000 up to BBBB) ¹⁸
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 13 (0000 up to CCCC) ¹⁹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 14 (0000 up to DDDD) ²⁰
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 15 (0000 up to EEEE) ²¹
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (0000 up to FFFF) ²²

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (completing the base 11 up to 16 series):

Date	Title
09-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 11 up to 16 (0000 up to XXXX) ²³

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (extending the base 16 series):

Date	Title
04-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 16 (-FFFFFF up to FFFFF) ²⁴

Authors published one paper on Figshare/Zenodo (focusing on bases 17 through 36):

Date	Title
23-01-2019	Crazy Sequential Representations: Base 17 up to 36 (0000 up to #####) ²⁵

Note

Previously authors used 'XXXX' as placeholder for the highest integer representable by four concatenated digits, thus $AAAA_{11}$, $BBBB_{12}$, $CCCC_{13}$, $DDDD_{14}$, $EEEE_{15}$ and $FFFF_{16}$ in base 11, 12, 13, 14, 15 and 16 respectively. In the context of base 11 up to 33, the 'XXXX' placeholder is unambiguous, as 'XXXX' cannot represent a valid integer.

However, in the context of base 34 and up, the 'XXXX' placeholder becomes ambiguous, as 'XXXX' can be interpreted as valid integer, for example $XXXX_{36}$ in case of base 36.

Within this manuscript authors used '#####' as placeholder for the highest integer representable by four concatenated digits, for example $ZZZZ_{36}$ in case of base 36 and $zzzz_{62}$ in case of base 62. Authors used the following digits for higher bases:

1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, J, K, L, M, N, O, P, Q, R, S, T, U, V, W, X, Y, Z, a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j, k, l, m, n, o, p, q, r, s, t, u, v, w, x, y, z

Examples - Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 10 crazy sequential representations (increasing and decreasing):

2671₁₀	48₁₀
$1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*89_{10}$	$9_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$

Examples - Non-Decimal Crazy Sequential Representations

Two valid base 11 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

5491₁₀	4142₁₁	378₁₀	314₁₁
$-1_{11}/2_{11}*(3_{11}-4_{11}+5_{11})^6+7_{11}*89A$		$A9_{11}^{(8_{11}-7_{11})}*6_{11}/(-5_{11}+4_{11}+3_{11})+21_{11}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1077_{10}$		$119_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 12 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

6853₁₀	3B71₁₂	419₁₀	2AB₁₂
$-1_{12}/2_{12}*(3_{12}-4_{12}+5_{12})^6+7_{12}*89A_{12}+B_{12}$		$B_{12}+A9_{12}^{(8_{12}-7_{12})}*6_{12}/(-5_{12}+4_{12}+3_{12})+21_{12}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1270_{10}+11_{10}$		$11_{10}+129_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 13 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

8460₁₀	3B0A₁₃	605₁₀	377₁₃
$-1_{13}/2_{13}*(3_{13}-4_{13}+5_{13})^6+7_{13}*89A_{13}+BC_{13}$		$CB_{13}+A9_{13}^{(8_{13}-7_{13})}*6_{13}/(-5_{13}+4_{13}+3_{13})+21_{13}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1479_{10}+155_{10}$		$167_{10}+139_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 14 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

12217₁₀	4649₁₄	302₁₀	178₁₄
$-1_{14}/2_{14}*(3_{14}-4_{14}+5_{14})^6+7_{14}*89A_{14}+BCD_{14}$		$D_{14}-CB_{14}+A9_{14}^{(8_{14}-7_{14})}*6_{14}/(-5_{14}+4_{14}+3_{14})+21_{14}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1704_{10}+2337_{10}$		$13_{10}-179_{10}+149_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 15 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

14221₁₀	4331₁₅	530₁₀	255₁₅
$-1_{15}/2_{15}*(3_{15}-4_{15}+5_{15})^6+7_{15}*89A_{15}+BCD_{15}-E_{15}$		$ED_{15}-CB_{15}+A9_{15}^{(8_{15}-7_{15})}*6_{15}/(-5_{15}+4_{15}+3_{15})+21_{15}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*1945_{10}+2668_{10}-14_{10}$		$223_{10}-191_{10}+159_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Two valid base 16 crazy sequential representations, and their base 10 representation:

16148₁₀	3F14₁₆	4402₁₀	1132₁₆
$-1_{16}/2_{16}*(3_{16}-4_{16}+5_{16})^6+7_{16}*89A_{16}+BCD_{16}-EF_{16}$		$FED_{16}-CB_{16}+A9_{16}^{(8_{16}-7_{16})}*6_{16}/(-5_{16}+4_{16}+3_{16})+21_{16}$	
$-1_{10}/2_{10}*(3_{10}-4_{10}+5_{10})^6+7_{10}*2202_{10}+3021_{10}-239_{10}$		$4077_{10}-203_{10}+169_{10}^{(8_{10}-7_{10})}*6_{10}/(-5_{10}+4_{10}+3_{10})+21_{10}$	

Definition - Base 16 Crazy Sequential Representation

Valid mathematical expression, thus well-formed interpretable syntactic construct.
 Evaluation results is an integer value, thus a number without a fractional component.
 Notation as used by most programming languages, thus restricted to following characters:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	A	B	C	D	E	F	+	-	*	/	^	(	)
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Digits 1 up to F occur in **increasing** or **decreasing** order:

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BCD-EF$	$FED-CB+A9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$
-------------------------------	-----------------------------------

Digits represent **single-digit** or **multi-digit** numbers (concatenation of digits is allowed):

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BCD-EF$	$FED-CB+A9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$
-------------------------------	-----------------------------------

Numbers occur in **positive form** or **negative form** (negation of numbers by “-” is allowed).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BCD-EF$	$FED-CB+A9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$
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Allowed operations; **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication**, **division** and/or **exponentiation**.

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BCD-EF$	$FED-CB+A9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$
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Order of evaluation may be influenced by **parentheses** (also nested parentheses).

$-1/2*(3-4+5)^6+7*89A+BCD-EF$	$FED-CB+A9^{(8-7)*6}/(-5+4+3)+21$
-------------------------------	-----------------------------------

Representations with **negation** of **segments in brackets** are referred to as “pseudo”.

$(1+2-3)*(45*-(6^7)+8-9ABCDEF)$	$(FEDCBA98+7*-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45/-(6^7)+8-9ABCDEF)$	$(FEDCBA98+7/-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$(1+2-3)*(45^-(6^7)+8-9ABCDEF)$	$(FEDCBA98+7^-(6^5)+4)*(3-2-1)$
$-(1+2+3)*(45^(6^7)+8-9ABCDEF)$	$(FEDCBA98+7^(6^5)+4)*(-(3-2)+1)$
$-(1-2+234*(6-7-8+9)*ABCDEF)$	$-(FEDCBA*(9-8-7+6)*543-2+1)$

Representations without negation of segments in brackets are referred to as “genuine”.

Definition - Base 17 up to 62 Crazy Sequential Representations

Identical to base 16 crazy sequential representations, but more digits allowed:

17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39
1-G	1-H	1-I	1-J	1-K	1-L	1-M	1-N	1-O	1-P	1-Q	1-R	1-S	1-T	1-U	1-V	1-W	1-X	1-Y	1-Z	1-a	1-b	1-c
40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62
1-d	1-e	1-f	1-g	1-h	1-i	1-j	1-k	1-l	1-m	1-n	1-o	1-p	1-q	1-r	1-s	1-t	1-u	1-v	1-w	1-z	1-y	1-z

Aim

Identify genuine base 17 up to 62 crazy sequential representations for '0000 up to #####'

- Genuine base 17 crazy sequential representations for 0000 up to GGGG
- Genuine base 18 crazy sequential representations for 0000 up to HHHH
- [..] [....] [....]
- Genuine base 61 crazy sequential representations for 0000 up to yyyy
- Genuine base 62 crazy sequential representations for 0000 up to zzzz

Generalization

Given that...

$((X+0)-(X+1)-(X+2)+(X+3))$	$== 0$
$((X+0)-(X+1)-(X+2)+(X+3))*(...)$	$== 0$
$((X+3)-(X+2)-(X+1)+(X+0))$	$== 0$
$(...)*((X+3)-(X+2)-(X+1)+(X+0))$	$== 0$

Any base 'n' crazy sequential representation without concatenation...

248_{10}	$1/2*3*4^5/6-7+8-9$
150_{10}	$9*8+7*6+5+4^3/2-1$
374_{10}	$(1+2*3)^4-5*(6+7*8)+9-(A+B*C*D)$
343_{10}	$D+C*(B*A)/(9*8-7-6*(5+4)-3*2-1)$

...can be converted to a base 'n+4' crazy sequential representation...

248_{10}	$1/2*3*4^5/6-7+8-9+(A-B-C+D)$
150_{10}	$(D-C-B+A)+9*8+7*6+5+4^3/2-1$
374_{10}	$(1+2*3)^4-5*(6+7*8)+9-(A+B*C*D)+(E-F-G+H)$
343_{10}	$(D-C-B+A)+D+C*(B*A)/(9*8-7-6*(5+4)-3*2-1)$

...and a base '>n+4' crazy sequential representation...

248_{10}	$1/2*3*4^5/6-7+8-9+(A-B-C+D)*(E...)$
150_{10}	$(...E)*(D-C-B+A)+9*8+7*6+5+4^3/2-1$
374_{10}	$(1+2*3)^4-5*(6+7*8)+9-(A+B*C*D)+(E-F-G+H)*(I...)$
343_{10}	$(...I)*(D-C-B+A)+D+C*(B*A)/(9*8-7-6*(5+4)-3*2-1)$

...by using the '(digit-digit-digit+digit)' construct, which always evaluates to zero...

248_{10}	$(248_{10})+(0)$
150_{10}	$(0)+(150_{10})$
374_{10}	$(375_{10})+(0)$
343_{10}	$(0)+(343_{10})$

...and therefor never influences the evaluation result.

Therefor the '0000 up to #####' range can be completed for base 17 up to 62 by identifying a relatively small set of genuine crazy sequential representations without concatenation:

From	To	To	Base	Series
000000 ₁₀	0083520 ₁₀	GGGG ₁₇	<= 13	Base 17 to 62
0083521 ₁₀	0104975 ₁₀	HHHH ₁₈	<= 14	Base 18 to 62
0104976 ₁₀	0130320 ₁₀	IIII ₁₉	<= 15	Base 19 to 62
0130321 ₁₀	0159999 ₁₀	JJJJ ₂₀	<= 16	Base 20 to 62
0160000 ₁₀	0194480 ₁₀	KKKK ₂₁	<= 17	Base 21 to 62
0194481 ₁₀	0234255 ₁₀	LLLL ₂₂	<= 18	Base 22 to 62
0234256 ₁₀	0279840 ₁₀	MMMM ₂₃	<= 19	Base 23 to 62
0279841 ₁₀	0331775 ₁₀	NNNN ₂₄	<= 20	Base 24 to 62
0331776 ₁₀	0390624 ₁₀	O000 ₂₅	<= 21	Base 25 to 62
0390625 ₁₀	0456975 ₁₀	PPPP ₂₆	<= 22	Base 26 to 62
0456976 ₁₀	0531440 ₁₀	QQQQ ₂₇	<= 23	Base 27 to 62
0531441 ₁₀	0614655 ₁₀	RRRR ₂₈	<= 24	Base 28 to 62
0614656 ₁₀	0707280 ₁₀	SSSS ₂₉	<= 25	Base 29 to 62
0707281 ₁₀	0809999 ₁₀	TTTT ₃₀	<= 26	Base 30 to 62
0810000 ₁₀	0923520 ₁₀	UUUU ₃₁	<= 27	Base 31 to 62
0923521 ₁₀	1048575 ₁₀	VVVV ₃₂	<= 28	Base 32 to 62
1048576 ₁₀	1185920 ₁₀	WWWV ₃₃	<= 29	Base 33 to 62
1185921 ₁₀	1336335 ₁₀	XXXX ₃₄	<= 30	Base 34 to 62
1336336 ₁₀	1500624 ₁₀	YYYY ₃₅	<= 31	Base 35 to 62
1500625 ₁₀	1679615 ₁₀	ZZZZ ₃₆	<= 32	Base 36 to 62
1679616 ₁₀	1874160 ₁₀	aaaa ₃₇	<= 33	Base 37 to 62
1874161 ₁₀	2085135 ₁₀	bbbb ₃₈	<= 34	Base 38 to 62
2085136 ₁₀	2313440 ₁₀	cccc ₃₉	<= 35	Base 39 to 62
2313441 ₁₀	2559999 ₁₀	dddd ₄₀	<= 36	Base 40 to 62
2560000 ₁₀	2825760 ₁₀	eeee ₄₁	<= 37	Base 41 to 62
2825761 ₁₀	3111695 ₁₀	ffff ₄₂	<= 38	Base 42 to 62
3111696 ₁₀	3418800 ₁₀	gggg ₄₃	<= 39	Base 43 to 62
3418801 ₁₀	3748095 ₁₀	hhhh ₄₄	<= 40	Base 44 to 62
3748096 ₁₀	4100624 ₁₀	iiii ₄₅	<= 41	Base 45 to 62
4100625 ₁₀	4477455 ₁₀	jjjj ₄₆	<= 42	Base 46 to 62
4477456 ₁₀	4879680 ₁₀	kkkk ₄₇	<= 43	Base 47 to 62
4879681 ₁₀	5308415 ₁₀	llll ₄₈	<= 44	Base 48 to 62
5308416 ₁₀	5764800 ₁₀	mmmm ₄₉	<= 45	Base 49 to 62
5764801 ₁₀	6249999 ₁₀	nnnn ₅₀	<= 46	Base 50 to 62
6250000 ₁₀	6765200 ₁₀	oooo ₅₁	<= 47	Base 51 to 62
6765201 ₁₀	7311615 ₁₀	pppp ₅₂	<= 48	Base 52 to 62
7311616 ₁₀	7890480 ₁₀	qqqq ₅₃	<= 49	Base 53 to 62
7890481 ₁₀	8503055 ₁₀	rrrr ₅₄	<= 50	Base 54 to 62
8503056 ₁₀	9150624 ₁₀	ssss ₅₅	<= 51	Base 55 to 62
9150625 ₁₀	9834495 ₁₀	tttt ₅₆	<= 52	Base 56 to 62
9834496 ₁₀	10556000 ₁₀	uuuu ₅₇	<= 53	Base 57 to 62
10556001 ₁₀	11316495 ₁₀	vvvv ₅₈	<= 54	Base 58 to 62
11316496 ₁₀	12117360 ₁₀	wwwv ₅₉	<= 55	Base 59 to 62
12117361 ₁₀	12959999 ₁₀	xxxx ₆₀	<= 56	Base 60 to 62
12960000 ₁₀	13845840 ₁₀	yyyy ₆₁	<= 57	Base 61 to 62
13845841 ₁₀	14776335 ₁₀	zzzz ₆₂	<= 58	Base 62 to 62

For example, genuine base 17 up to 62 crazy sequential representations for 83800_{10} can be derived from two genuine base 11 crazy sequential representations without concatenation:

Integer	Base	Genuine Crazy Sequential Representation
83800_{10}	11	$-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A$
	17	$-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-C-D+E)*(FG)$
	18	$-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-C-D+E)*(FGH)$
	19	$-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-C-D+E)*(FGHI)$
	29	$-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-C-D+E)*(FGHIJ)$
	21	$-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-C-D+E)*(FGHIJK)$
	[...]	[.....]
	35	$-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-C-D+E)*(FG...Y)$
	36	$-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-C-D+E)*(FG...Z)$
	[...]	[.....]
	61	$-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-C-D+E)*(FG...y)$
62	$-1*(2-3*(4-5*(-6-7*8)*9))*A+(B-C-D+E)*(FG...z)$	
83800_{10}	11	$A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^{-4+3-2}+1))$
	17	$(GF)*(E-D-C+B)+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^{-4+3-2}+1))$
	18	$(HGF)*(E-D-C+B)+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^{-4+3-2}+1))$
	19	$(IHGF)*(E-D-C+B)+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^{-4+3-2}+1))$
	29	$(JIHGF)*(E-D-C+B)+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^{-4+3-2}+1))$
	21	$(KJIHGF)*(E-D-C+B)+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^{-4+3-2}+1))$
	[...]	[.....]
	35	$(Y...GF)*(E-D-C+B)+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^{-4+3-2}+1))$
	36	$(Z...GF)*(E-D-C+B)+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^{-4+3-2}+1))$
	[...]	[.....]
	61	$(y...GF)*(E-D-C+B)+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^{-4+3-2}+1))$
62	$(z...GF)*(E-D-C+B)+A-9*(8-(7/(6+5)^{-4+3-2}+1))$	

Results

The '0000 up to #####' range for base 17 up to 36, as published previously, was improved. The '0000 up to #####' range for base 37 up to 62, was completed (for the first time).

Increasing variants were tabulated as follows:

Integer	Genuine Crazy Sequential Representation
11212 ₁₀	1*2*(3+4+(5+6)*7*8*9)+A*B+(C-D-E+F)*...
13938 ₁₀	(1+2)^(3+4)*5+6*7*8*9-A-B+(C-D-E+F)*...
22207 ₁₀	(1+2^3)^4-5^6*(7-8)^9+A+B+(C-D-E+F)*...

In order to 'increase the base' insert 'sufficient digits' at the '...' position:

Base	Integer	Integer	Genuine Crazy Sequential Representation
17	24D9 ₁₇	11212 ₁₀	1*2*(3+4+(5+6)*7*8*9)+A*B+(C-D-E+F)*G
18	1GAG ₁₈	11212 ₁₀	1*2*(3+4+(5+6)*7*8*9)+A*B+(C-D-E+F)*GH
19	1C12 ₁₉	11212 ₁₀	1*2*(3+4+(5+6)*7*8*9)+A*B+(C-D-E+F)*GHI
20	180C ₂₀	11212 ₁₀	1*2*(3+4+(5+6)*7*8*9)+A*B+(C-D-E+F)*GHIJ
[..]	[.....]	[.....]	[.....]
36	08NG ₃₆	11212 ₁₀	1*2*(3+4+(5+6)*7*8*9)+A*B+(C-D-E+F)*G..Z
[..]	[.....]	[.....]	[.....]
62	02uq ₆₂	11212 ₁₀	1*2*(3+4+(5+6)*7*8*9)+A*B+(C-D-E+F)*G..z

Decreasing variants were tabulated as follows:

Integer	Genuine Crazy Sequential Representation
13874 ₁₀	...*(F-E-D+C)+B+A-9*8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1
18268 ₁₀	...*(F-E-D+C)+B*A+9+(8+7*6^5+4+3)/(2+1)
43402 ₁₀	...*(F-E-D+C)+B-A-9*(8*7-(6+5)^4/3+2)^1

In order to 'increase the base' insert 'sufficient digits' at the '...' position;

Base	Integer	Integer	Genuine Crazy Sequential Representation
17	2E02 ₁₇	13874 ₁₀	...G*(F-E-D+C)+B+A-9*8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1
18	26EE ₁₈	13874 ₁₀	..HG*(F-E-D+C)+B+A-9*8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1
19	2084 ₁₉	13874 ₁₀	.IHG*(F-E-D+C)+B+A-9*8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1
20	1EDE ₂₀	13874 ₁₀	JIHG*(F-E-D+C)+B+A-9*8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1
[..]	[.....]	[.....]	[.....]
36	0APE ₃₆	13874 ₁₀	Z..G*(F-E-D+C)+B+A-9*8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1
[..]	[.....]	[.....]	[.....]
36	03bm ₆₂	13874 ₁₀	z..G*(F-E-D+C)+B+A-9*8+(7-(6-5+4)^3)^2+1

Obviously, in case there is no need to 'increase the base' the '*...' part can be ignored:

Base	Integer	Integer	Genuine Crazy Sequential Representation
17	254F ₁₇	0011354 ₁₀	1^2+3/4*5*6*7*8*9-A+B+C+(D-E-F+G)*...
17	254G ₁₇	0011355 ₁₀	1*2+3/4*5*6*7*8*9-A+B+C+(D-E-F+G)*...
17	2550 ₁₇	0011356 ₁₀	1+2+3/4*5*6*7*8*9-A+B+C+(D-E-F+G)*...

Notes

Authors consider genuine crazy sequential representations to be proof-of-work, as identification is computationally expensive, while verification is trivial. Authors did not simplify and/or optimize the crazy sequential representations.

In order to complete the '0000 up to ####' range for base 17 up to 62, crazy sequential representations for 0_{10} up to 14776335_{10} were required. However, crazy sequential representations for 0_{10} up to 16796159_{10} were identified during analysis, and therefor tabulated in the supplement. All crazy sequential representations are in base thirty-six or lower.

Significant shorter crazy sequential representations do exists, and can be easily derived from the present series, for example:

Integer	Genuine Crazy Sequential Representation
1954098_{10}	$\dots*(T-S-R+Q)+((P+0)-((N-M)*(L+K)))+(J-(I+H+G-F)+E+D)*(-C+B+A*9+(8+7)/6*(5^{(4+3)+2+1}))$
1954097_{10}	$\dots*(G-F-E+D)+C*B+A*9*8*7/6+5^{(4+3+2*1)}$
1954098_{10}	$\dots*(G-F-E+D)+C*B+A*9*8*7/6+5^{(4+3+2)+1}$
6705409_{10}	$\dots*(X-W-V+U)+T+S+R-(Q+P)-0+(-N-(M-L+K-J-I-H))*(G*F-E-D-C+B*A*(9*8*7*6+5*4+3)*2-1)$
6705410_{10}	$\dots*(J-I-H+G)-F-E*D*C-B+A*(9-8+(7*(6*5*4-3))^{2/1})$
6705409_{10}	$\dots*(J-I-H+G)-F-E*D*C-B+A*(9-8+(7*(6*5*4-3))^{2})-1$

Previously authors used the '(digit-(digit+digit-digit))' construct, which was now replaced by the '(digit-digit-digit+digit)' construct.

Integer	Genuine Crazy Sequential Representation
248_{10}	$1/2*3*4^5/6-7+8-9+(A-(B+C-D))*\dots$
248_{10}	$1/2*3*4^5/6-7+8-9+(A-B-C+D))*\dots$

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